

Maximum Angle

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We look at the following figure:

$$c_1 + c_2 = c$$

h and c are constant. Now we search for the maximum of γ in dependence of c_1 . We recognize:

$$\gamma = \arctan\left(\frac{c_1}{h}\right) + \arctan\left(\frac{c - c_1}{h}\right) \quad c_1 \in [0, c]$$

Now we calculate the derivation to c_1 :

$$\frac{d\gamma}{dc_1} = \frac{\frac{1}{h}}{1 + \frac{c_1^2}{h^2}} + \frac{-\frac{1}{h}}{1 + \left(\frac{c - c_1}{h}\right)^2}$$

The necessary criterion of local extrema is:

$$\frac{d\gamma}{dc_1} = 0$$

We get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{c_1^2}{h^2}} - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(c - c_1)^2}{h^2}} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{(c - c_1)^2}{h^2} - 1 - \frac{c_1^2}{h^2} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

It follows:

$$(c - c_1)^2 = c_1^2$$

The only ingenious solving is:

$$c - c_1 = c_1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad c = 2 \cdot c_1$$

and $c_2 = c_1$

At the isosceles triangle we have got the maximum angle.

In this case we must calculate the 2. derivation. We use the reciprocal rule:

$$\left(\frac{1}{g}\right)' = \frac{-g'}{g^2}$$

It follows:

$$\frac{d^2\gamma}{dc_1^2} = \frac{-1}{h^3} \cdot \left(\frac{2c}{\left(1 + \frac{c^2}{h^2}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{2 \cdot (c - c_1)}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{c-c_1}{h}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right)$$

with $c_1 = \frac{c}{2}$:

$$\frac{d^2\gamma}{dc_1^2} \left(\frac{c}{2}\right) < 0$$

So we have got a local maximum.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder, "Special extreme value problems and extremum principles", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002